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D5.7 – Final version of the Decision Support Framework (DSF) published and usage guidance for the end-users

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Executive Summary

The Decision Support Framework (DSF) is a digital tool¹ developed within the PROMISCES project to support decision-making in managing persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic substances (PM(T)s) in the environment. These PM(T) substances pose significant challenges in the transition to a safe circular economy, as they are difficult to monitor and mitigate. The DSF provides a structured approach for diagnosing substances, identifying solutions, and formulating strategies to ensure the safe reuse and recovery of resources while minimizing environmental and human health risks. By integrating research outcomes, external databases, and stakeholder input, the DSF serves as a user-friendly, interactive platform that enhances accessibility and usability for decision-makers. It is possible to access the DSF using the current link available [here](#).

The DSF is designed to assist regulatory authorities, industry professionals, and researchers in managing the risks of PM(T) substances in the soil-sediment-water cycle. The DSF is structured into five modules:

- 1) The *PMT assessment* module which can be used by users to verify if a substance is persistent, mobile, and/or toxic according to multiple data sources,
- 2) The *Diagnosis* module assists the user in getting a personalized diagnosis for a PM(T) case to support solution assessment,
- 3) The *Solutions* module helps to find solutions for preventing, assessing, monitoring and treating PM(T) substances and
- 4) The *Strategies* module provides guidance and examples of developing strategies for PMT substances across sectors.
- 5) The *Search Substances* module can be used to explore PM(T) chemicals across various chemical classes and sectors of use.

The DSF is based on activities in all tasks of work package (WP) 5 and complemented with results from all other PROMISCES WPs and case studies (CS). The platform enables users to visualize data, compare scenarios, and make informed decisions based on scientific evidence, practical/technical implications, and regulatory requirements. This report is divided into three parts. The objectives of the different parts are to provide usage information for potential users of the DSF, to describe the process followed in creating the DSF and to provide technical information useful for developers.

The development of the DSF followed a cascade approach, starting with low fidelity prototyping to define the core functionalities, followed by high-fidelity prototyping to refine the user interface and interactions. The tool was then developed through three iterative coding phases, incorporating feedback from usability tests to improve its design, functionality, and overall user experience.

The DSF was evaluated throughout the project by all project partners as well as by end-users of the DSF. Details on the testing and included end-users are provided in this report (chapter 6).

The DSF is coded in two different code directories: the backend and the frontend.

¹ During the course of the project the tool was available at <https://promisces.eurecatprojects.com/#/>. The current link is available via <https://promisces.eu/Results/Tools/PROMISCES+DSF.html>.

The backend is responsible for data processing, storage, and retrieval. Built using Java Spring Boot, it integrates multiple external data sources, including the NORMAN Database and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) database, and performs calculations necessary for substance classification, similarity analysis, and ranking functionalities. The backend provides HTTP endpoints that enable the frontend to access data efficiently while optimizing system performance.

On the frontend, the DSF is built using Angular and TypeScript, with PrimeNG components for UI elements and Plotly for data visualization. This interactive interface allows users to search for substances, assess chemical properties, explore mitigation strategies, and create customized risk management plans. The frontend design prioritizes clarity, usability, and accessibility, ensuring that stakeholders can navigate the tool seamlessly and extract valuable insights.

For deployment, the DSF uses Docker and Docker Compose, ensuring a streamlined, scalable, and easily reproducible setup. The system is composed of four key containers:

1. PostgreSQL Database – Stores all relevant data for efficient querying.
2. Java Spring Boot Backend – Manages data processing and retrieval.
3. Python Web Service – Handles advanced calculations, such as substance similarity analysis.
4. Angular Frontend with Nginx – Provides a responsive, user-friendly interface.

Until the end of the PROMISCES project, the DSF is deployed on Eurecat servers for testing and demonstrations, but it can be easily replicated on other infrastructures. The open-source code is publicly available on GitHub², allowing for further development, collaboration, and integration into external platforms.

After the end of the project, the DSF is expected to evolve further through collaboration with the NORMAN network, ensuring long-term maintenance and integration into its database system. Future enhancements may include improved data visualization, optimized performance, better regulatory alignment, and AI-powered interactive learning functionalities to assist users in decision-making.

² <https://github.com/Applied-Artificial-Intelligence-Eurecat/Promisces-Front> and <https://github.com/Applied-Artificial-Intelligence-Eurecat/Promisces-back>

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Acronyms and abbreviations

CAS Number	Unique identifier for chemical substances, assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service
CE Route	Circular Economy Route
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DSF	Decision Support Framework
EC Number	Unique identifier for chemical substances, assigned by the European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EMPODAT	NORMAN Chemical Occurrence Database
EU	European Union
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Secure Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JPA	Java Persistence API
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
PM(T)s	Persistent, Mobile and Potentially Toxic Substances
PROMISCES	Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SLE	NORMAN Suspect List Exchange
SMILES	Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification
SSbD	Sustainable-by-design
SusDat	NORMAN Substance Database
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP5	Work Package 5

1 Introduction

1.1 Background: Context and Relevance

To transition towards a circular economy in the soil-sediment-water environment, persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic substances (PM(T)s) present a systematic challenge due to the lack of adequate treatment, monitoring, and risk assessment tools. This creates significant obstacles for regulatory authorities, hindering their ability to provide clear guidance on effectively addressing or treating these substances within circular economy frameworks and industrial settings. To address these challenges, the PROMISCES project aims to deliver innovative technical solutions that support the ambitions outlined in the Green Deal and related regulations.

One of PROMISCES objectives is to support decision-making on the prevention and reduction of critical persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic substances (PM(T)s) in the environment, enabling the safe reuse and recovery of resources within a circular economy. This is achieved by developing a novel decision support framework (DSF) that includes five modules:

- 1) The *PMT assessment* module which can be used by users to verify if a substance is persistent, mobile, and/or toxic according to multiple data sources,
- 2) The *Diagnosis* module assists the user in getting a personalized diagnosis for a PM(T) case to support solution assessment,
- 3) The *Solutions* module helps to find solutions for preventing, assessing, monitoring and treating PM(T) substances, and
- 4) The *Strategies* module provides guidance and examples of developing strategies for PMT substances across sectors.
- 5) The *Search Substances* module can be used to explore PM(T) chemicals across various chemical classes and sectors of use.

The DSF thereby integrates considerations such as cost, social benefits, stakeholder concerns, and the feasibility of implementation of solutions to co-create comprehensive risk management strategies. By enabling the assessment of different scenarios for PM(T) reduction and their associated risks to ecosystems and human health, PROMISCES seeks to address both short-term mitigation and long-term prevention of PM(T) pollution from a system-wide perspective.

The DSF consolidates the project outcomes by providing a user-friendly interactive platform to access all the solutions and data generated within PROMISCES, complementing them with information generated throughout the project and information gathered from external data sources. The tool enables stakeholders to study areas of concern, assess the efficacy of proposed solutions, and make informed, data-driven decisions.

1.2 Developing the Decision Support Framework (DSF)

The developed DSF addresses the three major theoretical pillars identified: diagnosing potential PM(T) substances, proposing solutions to minimize their impact, and formulating strategies for managing their risks. The tool has been designed to translate the theoretical concepts within these blocks into a digital format, enabling users to interact intuitively with each component and facilitating navigation across these key areas.

The digital tool is divided into two main components: the backend and the frontend. The backend manages data processing and storage, handling raw data, retrieving information from external servers, and storing all the data required for the tool's functionality. It is also responsible for performing calculations and selecting the appropriate data to provide to the user via the frontend. The frontend serves as the user interface, allowing users to visualize the data and theoretical information developed during the project. Its primary goal is to provide clear explanations and facilitate human-computer interaction, supporting users in making informed decisions effectively and efficiently.

The design and development of this tool followed a cascade approach, implemented in a staggered manner. It began with the initial design defined within the project, which was further refined through the insights and expertise contributed by other project members. This design evolved into a prototype that end-users evaluated over two iterations. Each iteration helped identify usability issues within the system, enabling iterative improvements to enhance its functionality and user experience.

1.3 Goals and organization of this deliverable

This deliverable aims to outline the digital tool's development process and provide guidance on its usage. The document is divided into several chapters that can be divided into three main parts. The first part presents the objectives of the tool and serves as a guide for users on how to use the tool (Chapter 2). The second part focuses on the development process (Chapters 3 and 4), detailing the development methodology and the testing process. The third part describes different technical information relevant for developers, such as technical descriptions of the backend and frontend of the different modules (Chapter 5), explanations on the data acquisition process (Chapter 6) and a description on the entire deploying process of the DSF (Chapter 7). Finally, the document concludes with an outline of the tool's future beyond the project, including potential implementations and enhancements to expand its functionalities (Chapter 8).

This deliverable consolidates and utilizes the knowledge generated in the PROMISCES project. The following deliverables are at the core of the DSF:

- D5.1 Mapping of EU PM(T) concerns, including essential uses,
- D5.2 Portal of PM(T) substitution,
- D5.3 Policy brief on PM(T) concerns and actions in EU,
- D5.4 Reports on solution strategies to reach a non-toxic environment for 5 PM(T) uses from a system perspective,
- D5.5 Map of potential for PM(T) substitution in one high-stake sector,
- D5.6 Guidance on transdisciplinary co-creation of solution strategies to reach a non-toxic environment and safely reuse resources,

By April 2025, all reports are available on the PROMISCES Zenodo website³. The website D5.2 is available via this link: <https://substitution-perfluores.ineris.fr/en>.

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/promisces/records>

2 User guidelines

The DSF consists of five modules: PMT assessment, Diagnosis, Solutions, Strategies and Search Substances. Each module is accessed through its separate screen in the DSF. In addition to one screen for each module, the DSF has two extra screens, Homepage and About, to facilitate navigation through the DSF and provide information on the sources of the data available in the DSF. In the following sections, general descriptions of these modules and screens are presented.⁴ Examples of use cases where the DSF provides effective solutions are available on [Zenodo](#). It is possible to access the DSF using the link available here: <https://promiscses.eu/Results/Tools/PROMISCSES+DSF.html>.

2.1 Homepage

The homepage is the first page the user encounters upon opening the tool. It provides an overview of the tool's main objective and introduces its key functionalities, aiming to facilitate user navigation. Below the initial explanations, the different modules that comprise the tool are displayed, each with its respective link. Additionally, a navigation bar, shared across all sections, allows users to easily access different parts of the tool.

2.2 PMT assessment

- **Aim and general description of the module.**

Users can use this module to verify if a substance is persistent, mobile, and/or toxic according to multiple data sources. By determining these characteristics, the user can better understand the potential impact and develop appropriate response strategies. The profile of the substance is defined following the criteria in Regulation (EU) 2024/2865 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP). For substance classification, three different scenarios are proposed:

1. Conservative Scenario: Selects the highest score based on predicted data.
2. Average Scenario: Calculates the average score based on at least two data sources for predicted data.
3. Robust Scenario: Selects the highest score based on experimental data.

Details are provided on the following aspects:

- Scenarios for substance classification and scoring based on data quality and availability.
- P, M, T Score calculations.
- The EU CLP regulation criteria for Toxicity.

⁴ During the project the tool is available at <https://promiscses.eurecatprojects.com/#/>.

- Usage

The user can navigate to the PMT assessment. Here, users can search for a substance or a group of substances using the substance name, InChIKey (International Chemical Identifier), or CAS number (but acronyms like PFOA are not allowed). The user can also partially specify these variables, and the search will return all substances that match the patterns provided. The results, whether for a single substance or multiple substances, are displayed in a 2D scatter plot which places persistence on the X-axis and mobility on the Y-axis, with different background colors indicating classifications such as persistent, mobile, very persistent, very mobile, persistent and mobile, and very persistent and very mobile. Additionally, substance toxicity is represented by the color of the dots—black for toxic substances and green for non-toxic ones.

Figure 1 - Result of searching for substances starting with "Sul" in the PMT assessment.

Users can select which of the three scenarios for score calculation they would like to see the results for. As mentioned above, the scenarios include:

- a Conservative Scenario, that selects the highest score based on predicted data,
- an Average Scenario, that calculates the average score based on at least two data sources for predicted data, and
- a Robust Scenario that selects the highest score based on experimental data.

The plot is interactive, allowing users to click on a substance point to view its details. The substance details include key identifiers (such as the CAS number), persistence, mobility, and toxicity calculations for all three scenarios, as well as various classifications. Additionally, users can download all resulting substance data, which include even more information not displayed in the details section. This data can be exported as a .csv file, with the option to choose between comma or semicolon separators.

2.3 Diagnosis

- **Aim and general description of the module.**

The aim of the Diagnosis module is to get a personalized diagnosis for a PM(T) case to support solution assessment. It can be used by users if they are concerned about a specific substance as it helps the user to compare a substance's PM(T) properties with 30 structurally similar substances. Furthermore, the user can explore the substances' sectors of use. Also, it helps the user to understand alternatives for a substance and inform on what additional substances are worth including in monitoring campaigns. Finally, it shows the extent of PM(T) use across sectors. This information can be used to understand how widespread the use of a particular substance is. Listed below are the main goals of this module:

Substance identification: Enables users to search for substances using various attributes supporting both exact and partial matches.

Prioritization of substances: Provides a ranking system based on key properties (persistence, mobility, toxicity, and kemi-score) to highlight the most relevant substances for analysis.

Similarity analysis: Facilitates the identification of structurally similar substances to support broader assessment.

Data visualization: Offers different data visualizations to enhance data comprehension.

- **Usage**

The diagnosis section allows users to search for a specific substance, prompting the system to recommend related substances based on structural similarity (SMILES), as well as substances belonging to the same product category or sector of use. Similar substances are presented in a bar chart, where each bar corresponds to a substance. Users can reorder the bars according to persistence, mobility, toxicity, or Kemi score. Clicking on a bar reveals detailed information about the selected substance.

The product category (PC) and sector of use groupings are shown as two different bubble plots. In these plots, each bubble represents a PC or sector, with the X-axis showing the average persistence of all substances in that sector of use following the conservative scenario, the Y-axis showing the average mobility of all substances in that sector of use following the conservative scenario, and the bubble size indicating the number of substances within that group.

Figure 2 - Bubble chart REACH product category for substance "Caffeine".

2.4 Solution assessment

- **Aim and general description of the module.**

The Solution Assessment module aims to provide systematic approaches for managing PM(T) substances. It categorizes solutions into four key areas: Prevention, Monitoring, Risk Assessment, and Treatment, guiding users through measures to mitigate environmental and human health risks. The module aims to ensure that users can explore different types of solutions, from preventing PM(T) substance release to monitoring, assessing risks and implementing treatment solutions, when possible, tailored to specific circular economy routes.

The module provides users with links and tools based on the type of solution they seek. In specific cases, it also presents information through visual plots. Common user queries are addressed through:

- Redirections to tools that aid the prevention of PM(T) substances discharge into environment within the DSF or external resources.
- Visual overview of targeted monitoring data in the NORMAN EMPODAT database using various graphical formats such as tables and bar plots, including a download selected data option.
- Monitoring methodologies including sampling and analytical methodologies for industrial PM(T) and PFAS substances.
- Links to information sources, repositories, and external projects on the risk assessment of substances including mixture toxicity analysis.
- Efficient selection of a suitable technology based on treatment data related to a circular economy route.

- Usage

When the user enters the Solutions section, they are prompted to select a solution type from Prevention, Monitoring, Risk Assessment, or Treatment. Upon selection, a series of tailored questions and their answers are displayed. These questions not only provide theoretical insights but also offer access to various internal and external tools, visual representations of the NORMAN EMPODAT targeted monitoring data such as plots and tables with filters, and references to external portals for further exploration of relevant information regarding prevention and substitution. Examples of how the Solution assessment module can be applied to find solutions for five preselected substance-use combinations, including PFAS, are available in [Deliverable D5.4 - Solution strategies](#).

Figure 3 - Systemic view of the types of systematic solutions in the DSF (Each solution type is clickable).

2.5 Strategy creation

- **Aim and general description of the module.**

The Strategies module aims to guide decision-making by suggesting key elements to consider when selecting solutions. It helps to assess feasibility, effectiveness, and potential barriers across social, environmental, financial, technical, and regulatory aspects. By integrating solutions with strategic insights, stakeholders can develop comprehensive zero-pollution strategies tailored to specific circular economy routes and local contexts. This module provides access to relevant reference documents and links to external resources. Through this, stakeholders can explore different pathways for implementing zero-pollution strategies while considering feasibility, effectiveness, and potential barriers.

- **Usage**

The section provides resources and tools to help decision-makers develop their own strategies for managing PM(T) substances (Persistent, Mobile, and Toxic substances). It guides users toward different management approaches, such as remediation, prevention, monitoring, and hazard assessment, and links to key policy recommendations and regulatory frameworks that should accompany technical innovation. Furthermore, it offers support for co-creation processes, encouraging collaboration with local stakeholders to develop effective zero-pollution strategies. Several linked documents and case study summaries are served as practical references for shaping well-informed, actionable strategies.

Figure 4 - Information available on the Strategy Creation page.

2.6 Search substances

- **Aim and general description of the module.**

In this module, decision-makers can explore substances across various chemical classes, sectors of use and product categories. The substances and their physicochemical properties are based on the SusDat Database⁵.

- **Usage**

The substance search is designed to provide substances matching one or more user-defined parameters. The results can be viewed in various formats, such as tables or plots (3D plots and bar plots), and users can select a substance to explore its detailed information. Searches can be performed using various parameters, including Full Name, InChiKey, CAS Number, Substance Group, Predicted Parameters, Experimental Parameters, CE Route, Chemical Class, and Sector of Use. As mentioned in the PMT Assessment section, which uses the same function, parameters can be partially defined, and the search will return all substances that match.

Figure 5 - Example of a search query for substances of chemical class "Anthraquinone" used in sector "Building and construction work", which returns 2 substances.

2.7 “About” page

This final section is designed to provide links to the resources used in data development and the underlying theoretical concepts. It includes a table listing each resource by name, along with its corresponding link and a brief description outlining its contents. Furthermore, a link to the final version of this deliverable will be added to ensure users can find the user guidelines.

⁵ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/susdat/>

3 Development methodology

The development methodology followed during the project was aimed at designing and developing a tool to achieve the PROMISCES objective of "assessing risks and improving the management of PM(T) in a circular economy." Despite the objective, it was necessary first to consider what data was available and, second, to determine the calculations and visualizations that could be offered to users based on that data. Consequently, the development focused on designing a system that balances ease of use with the ability to present processed data in a way that maximizes its value.

The development process of the tool can be divided into the following key steps (see also Section 1.2):

- Low-fidelity prototype design.
- Key partners feedback gathering session.
- High-fidelity prototype design.
- Consortium feedback gathering session.
- First development iteration.
- BWB usability testing and feedback session.
- Second development iteration.
- Dutch chemical companies' usability testing.
- Final development and deployment.

The first step is referred to as low-fidelity prototyping. At the beginning of the project, multiple meetings were held to define the core modules of the tool and determine which basic functionalities should be designed initially. These modules, categorized into substances (later called diagnosis), solutions, and strategies, were outlined in an initial design known as a low-fidelity prototype. This prototype visually represented the potential structure of the graphic interface and enabled a quick discussion of initial ideas without the need to invest development time. Figure 6 presents the first version of the substances module in the prototype, where the module's requirements can be visually observed, including the ability to search for a list of substances using various input parameters. The prototype results for the remaining modules are provided in the appendix **Low-Fidelity Prototype**.

The screenshot shows the PROMISCES web interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'Home', 'Assessment', 'Profile', and 'Contact us'. Below the navigation, there are several search and filter fields: 'Substance Name', 'Type of solution', 'Solution name', 'Substance group', 'CE route', 'Chemical class', 'Sector of use', and 'Followed strategy'. A 'Search' button is located to the right of the 'Solution name' field. Below the search fields, there is a 'View as plot' button and a 'Page [1] / 171' indicator. The main content area displays a table with the following columns: 'Substance Name', 'Solution type', 'Solution name', and 'Strategy'. The table contains several rows, including 'Substance 1', 'Substance 2', 'Substance 3', and 'Substance 20'. The 'Solution type' column for 'Substance 1' contains the text 'More than 4...', and the 'Solution name' column contains 'More than X...'. The 'Strategy' column contains 'Partial text...'. There are blue arrow icons to the right of each row in the table.

Figure 6 - Low-fidelity prototype - Substances module.

Based on the feedback gathered by presenting the prototype to a small group from the consortium, the design evolved into a high-fidelity prototype. This version not only implemented visualizations but also included navigation between different sections. In this second stage, the tool was refined, improving the user interface design, which previously featured only basic colors and a rudimentary functionality structure. The results of this iteration were presented to the entire consortium, a key process in selecting the functionalities to be implemented, as it was tested by stakeholders responsible for generating the data to be utilized by the tool. Figure 7 shows the Substance search portal of the obtained prototype, featuring a well-defined structure, color scheme, and information layout. The entire prototype is attached in the appendix **High-Fidelity Prototype**.

The screenshot shows the 'Substance search portal' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the PROMISCES logo and links for Home, Assessment, Profile, and Contact. Below the navigation bar, the title 'Substance search portal' is displayed. A sub-header reads 'Introduce different information to find substances related to your case'. The search form includes several input fields and dropdown menus: 'Substance Name' (with a placeholder 'Type name here...'), 'Type of solution', 'Solution name', 'Substance group', 'CE route', 'Chemical class', 'sector of use', and 'Followed strategy' (with a placeholder 'Introduce keywords or strategy...'). There are 'Reset' and 'Search' buttons. Below the search form, the 'Results for Substances' section shows 'Substance 1 - 20 3423', 'Range of results: XX / XXX', 'Sort by' (dropdown), and 'Change view' (dropdown). A table displays the search results with columns for Substance, Solution type, Solution name, and Strategy. The table contains 10 rows of data, with the first row being 'Substance 1' and the others being 'Substance 2' through 'Substance 4'. Each row has a blue arrow icon to its right.

Substance	Solution type	Solution name	Strategy
Substance 1	More than 4...	More than x ...	Partial text
Substance 2			Partial text
Substance 3			Partial text
Substance 4	More than 4...		Partial text
Substance 4	More than 4...		Strategy
Substance 4	More than 4...		Strategy
Substance 4	More than 4...		Strategy
Substance 4	More than 4...		Strategy
Substance 4	More than 4...		Strategy
Substance 4	More than 4...		Strategy

Figure 7 - High-fidelity prototype - Substance module.

After the tool was designed and prototyped in the first two iterations, the initial round of development was conducted, establishing a basic structure for the webpage, which was prepared for evaluation by end-users in subsequent evaluation rounds (detailed in Chapter 4). Throughout the project, three development rounds were completed, each evaluated by end-users, with their feedback applied to enhance the user experience.

4 The DSF evaluation process

During the project, four evaluation iterations were conducted: two internal evaluations with project team members and two external evaluations with different end users. Each session had distinct objectives, as the evaluators had varying profiles and responsibilities for the system both within and outside the project. However, all sessions shared a common goal of refining and enhancing the system's functionalities. Specifically, the testing by project partners and end-users was conducted in 4 phases, namely:

1. In December 2022, the initial low-fidelity prototype was reviewed by WP leads.
2. In March 2023, the first high-fidelity prototype was reviewed by all project partners at the steering committee meeting in Ancona, gathering comprehensive feedback to refine features and optimize UI design.
3. In November 2023, the first usability test was performed with external users, specifically the drinking water utility of Berlin (BWB). The aim was to assess system usability and navigation, identifying necessary improvements. This testing was held at BWB headquarters in Berlin and 7 employees of BWB took part in the testing.
4. In April 2024, the second user testing session was conducted at Sitech in the Netherlands. The testing was performed with 4 people from Sitech and 1 employee of a chemical company at the Chemelot industrial site in Stein, NL. This final usability test was performed to validate previous enhancements and confirm improved user interaction and decision-making efficiency.

4.1 First evaluation – Low fidelity prototype

The first evaluation took place at the beginning of the project, during which a low-fidelity prototype and interaction designs between the data and system modules were available. Since selecting initial functionalities is a critical phase for establishing the tool's foundation, the decision was made to share the first design with a core group of project participants, familiarizing the most involved members with the process. The evaluation and feedback-gathering process was structured by explaining the system and encouraging discussion through prepared questions.

The specific goals of the first session were to:

1. Inform: Create feeling of shared ownership for the case study and work package leads with the DSF by involving them in the design process.
2. Critique: Receive feedback on the low-fidelity prototype and what should be improved in the high-fidelity prototype.

The discussion was arranged using the following questions:

- *Does the structure of the DSF make sense? What do you like about it?*
- *What features don't make sense?*
- *Are any relevant features missing currently? If so, which ones?*
- *If you had a magic wand, what would you change?*
- *Does this tool resemble anything you know? If yes, what?*

This workshop enabled initial improvements to the tool, particularly in areas related to interaction with certain functionalities, data visualization, and clarification of information available as input/output from the perspectives of data providers and end users.

4.2 Second evaluation – High-fidelity prototype

The second evaluation took place three months after the first evaluation, allowing enough time to incorporate the feedback received in the first evaluation. During this time, the low-fidelity prototype evolved into a high-fidelity prototype, not only integrating the new requested functionalities, but also refining the colors and screen interactions. This evaluation was carried out during the general assembly in Ancona with the whole consortium, splitting the consortium into twelve moderated groups that had to discuss several features to be implemented. Table 1 shows the screen, the feature and the feedback the stakeholder/user/partner provided, and the color indicates if a feedback was considered (green) or discarded (red). Feedback was mostly discarded due to technical unfeasibility, lack of data, or large requirements. Further information was gathered as metadata to work on it during the next development iteration.

Table 1 - Feedback obtained - High-fidelity prototype. In green: Considered. In red: Discarded.

Screen	Feature	Feedback from stakeholders/users
Homepage	Bar plot	Recommend searches depending on the stakeholder group. These recommendations should be the most common.
Homepage	Information source indication	To ensure the transparency of the data with the user, we should enable a part of the page where the sources are indicated.
Homepage	The link between solution and substance	To provide information to the final user on how this mapping is done.
Homepage	Bar plot	A reference compound could be added to understand the weighting system.
Homepage	Bar plot	Add information/explanation of each criterion.
Homepage	General	To have a more descriptive introduction page explaining to users who are less aware of the tool functionalities.
Homepage	Bar plot	Some criteria are yet to be defined. Different options suggested by the stakeholders.
Homepage	Bar plot	Sort substances by score: Highest scoring first. Even possibility to let the user decide the sorting mechanism.
Homepage	Bar plot	Nomenclature needs to be harmonized with REACH regulation.
Homepage	General	Allow users to download the data via Excel.
Homepage	Bar plot	Let the user add new criteria.
Homepage	General	Save/manage searches done by users and recommend based on history.

Screen	Feature	Feedback from stakeholders/users
General	General	To design and implement the searches/filters as much as possible to improve all the possible searches. Furthermore, add information on each filter.
Substance search portal	Search option	Search by CAS number
Substance search portal	Search option	Search by SMILES identification
Substance search portal	Search option	Search in batch mode "CAS;CAS;CAS;CAS"
Substance search portal	Search option	Search options should have an explanation
Substance search portal	Search option	Add matrix to search options (wastewater, soil, sediment, ...)
Substance search portal	Search option	Search using regulations.
Substance search portal	Results list	Let the user add substances to the favorite list
Substance search portal	Figure	Improve visualization of the 3D plots
Substance search portal	Results list	Add an option to show a list of compounds that are relevant to an industry.
Substance search portal	Bar plot	Add a bar plot visualization in the substance search portal
Check substance details	General	Recommendation of some external databases, to add information or to directly link to those databases.
Check substance details	Link	Link substance detail to an existing regulation.
Solution assessment	Search options	For the systematic solution Treatment use other search parameters like matrix, TRL, cost, ...
Solution assessment	Search options	Instead of applying for specific compounds, apply to groups.
Solution assessment	Criteria	Different options proposed to add as criteria.
Solution assessment	Results displayed	In the treatment module for the parameters cost and energy show range of values instead of just one.
Solution assessment	Results displayed	Sort results with different indices that the user can select.
Solution assessment	General	Add information on the search options used.
Solution assessment	Information links	Add references to technologies.
Substance identification	Plotting of compounds	What compounds should I be aware of and what solutions are available to treat them.

Screen	Feature	Feedback from stakeholders/users
Substance identification	Criteria selection	Add criteria selection based on regulations.
Substance identification	Filter options	Put and harmonize different filter options like CAS number, name, sector of use...
Substance identification	Add to favorite	Add substances to a preferred list for the user.
Substance identification	Graph options	Several recommendations on value representation on the plot, legends system, and plot filtering.

The working team later discussed the comments on these features internally to assess their feasibility in each case. Some features were discarded due to data unavailability or privacy concerns (e.g., avoiding the management of user profiles). The other features were later adapted differently to accommodate the user’s request.

The second evaluation served as a starting point for coding the first version of the DSF. The prototype defined the overall UI structure, and the evaluation output was used to refine and correct the expected features.

4.3 Third evaluation – First development iteration

The third evaluation took place months later, once the first version of the DSF was coded. It was conducted with external stakeholders and users, with the primary objective of assessing the system’s usability and identifying new features to improve the user experience.

The session was held in person at one of the project partner’s offices in Berlin and consisted of individual user tests divided into three phases: an explanation of the project and the purpose of the DSF, specific use case exercises, and one-on-one feedback sessions. This process provided both quantitative and qualitative feedback, gathered through discussions and observations of user behavior during the hands-on exercises.

Table 2 presents the exercises completed by each user. Seven testers participated, each allocated 30 minutes to perform tasks such as navigating the DSF, searching for substances, assessing substances and solutions, and downloading strategies. User feedback was collected through task difficulty ratings on a scale of 1 to 5, followed by an open discussion on potential improvements and the tool’s applicability in their workflow. Additionally, screen recordings (without audio or camera) were used to extract quantitative data on user learning and system understanding, ensuring anonymity and allowing participants the right to withdraw consent.

The quantitative metrics were:

- Pageviews: Represents the total number of times a page was viewed by users.
- Average Time for Exercise: The average duration (in seconds) that users spend on a specific exercise.
- Session Duration: The total amount of time (in seconds) a user spends during an entire session.
- Scroll Depth: Indicates how far users scroll down on a page (measured in percentage).
- Error Rate: The number of errors the user makes during task completion.
- Event Tracking: Monitors specific user interactions, such as button clicks, form submissions, or video plays.

- Number of Steps to Complete a Task: Measures the efficiency of task completion by counting the steps taken.

Table 2 - Use case exercises during the third evaluation. Some tasks are not relevant with the final version of the tool.

Task #	DSF page	Directions
1	Go to Homepage	Change substance criteria selection bars to fixed settings (persistence 10, mobility 8, toxicity 2). Check the details of the substance with highest persistence (which will be displayed in the bar graph below the selection bars).
2	Go to Substance search portal page	Go to the substance search portal and search for the substance perfluorooctanoic acid. Check the details of the substance.
3	Go to PMT identifier page	Search if substance perfluorooctanoic acid is toxic. Check the details of the substance – is the substance vPvM/PM/toxic/nontoxic?
4	Go to PMT assessment page	Find substances related to CE route B (Wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation). Check the details of the first resulting substance
5	Go to Possible Strategies page	Download Strategy 7 and open it.
6	Go to the Solution assessment page	Click on Route A, go to Emission prevention and then to the substitution portal (webpage of INERIS).

The usability test revealed key findings in user behavior while navigating the DSF. The first tester experienced difficulties due to a lack of explanation on the webpage and was noticeably nervous, leading to a longer session duration. In contrast, testers 4 and 5 were already familiar with the platform, and tester 7 demonstrated greater proficiency with digital tools compared to the others.

The analysis also showed that page views correlate with the error rate, suggesting that users who navigate more may struggle with the interface. Notably, the first tester extensively explored the webpage. Task 1 had the highest error rate, requiring more steps to complete and resulting in frequent mistakes. Similarly, task 2 showed recurring errors in substance name entry across multiple testers. Despite these variations, event tracking and the number of steps taken remained relatively consistent across participants. However, task 1 consistently required the most steps, as testers tended to make more errors and needed additional actions to complete their tasks.

After the evaluation session, a retrospective meeting on the testing was held, and solutions were identified to tackle the inefficiencies encountered.

Home Page:

- **Criteria confusion:** Users mistakenly selected “Criteria 4” instead of “Persistence”. -> Remove unused criteria names and display a range (0-10) under each criterion.
- **Barplot Visibility:** Users didn’t see changes in the barplot after setting criteria -> Options include adding a scroll message, reducing criteria section size, or placing criteria and barplot side by side.
- **Barplot Interaction:** Users were confused by the ability to move/maximize the barplot. -> Lock X and Y axes to prevent movement.
- **Clickable Bars:** Users didn’t realize they could click bars for details. -> Add a description indicating that bars are clickable.

Navigation & UI Elements:

- **Assessment Option Visibility:** Users didn’t realize they could select features in the “Assessment” section. -> Rename “Assessment” to “DSF Features” and replace the arrow with a dropdown icon. Keep in mind possible changes in future.

PMT Identifier & Assessment:

- **Scatterplot Navigation:** Users could zoom and move axes, causing confusion. -> Lock X and Y axes within a restricted range.
- **Dot Visibility:** Users struggled to see the scatterplot dots clearly. -> Increase dot size for better visibility.
- **Search Focus:** Users fixated on the “Search Substance” field before reading the guiding question. -> Remove default selection of “Yes” and let users choose their own preference.

Search Substance Portal:

- **Past Results Displayed Incorrectly:** Users saw previous results when searching for a new substance. → Ensure backend returns zero substances when no match is found.
- **Wildcard Search Misuse:** Users attempted to use * for partial matches. → Inform the user that name suggestions will appear for them.
- **Long Substance Names:** Users found it cumbersome to type long names. → Implement a dropdown with name suggestions for better search experience.

CE Route Naming & Data Representation:

- **CE Route Terminology:** Users didn’t understand “CE Route.” → Explain or rename the term for clarity.
- **Data Normalization:** Users struggled to compare persistence (P), mobility (M), and toxicity (T) values. → Normalize the data to enhance comparability.

This identified list of features was implemented in preparation of the fourth evaluation, aiming to check if these new additions improved the metrics gathered from the users and their impression of the system.

4.4 Fourth evaluation – Second development iteration

The fourth evaluation took place five months after the third. The aim was to evaluate the new features implemented between iterations, checking if the learning rate and usability improved with the new additions. It was again conducted with external end users. The methodology followed during the session was the same as the one during the third evaluation, modifying some tasks, defined in Table 3, to ensure that the implemented features were correctly tested.

Table 3 - Tasks done during the fourth evaluation.

Task #	DSF page	Directions
1	Go to Homepage	Change substance criteria selection bars to fixed settings (persistence 10, mobility 8, toxicity 2). Check the details of the substance with highest persistence
2	Go to Substance search portal page	Go to the substance search portal and search for the substance 'perfluorooctanoic acid'. Check the details of the substance
3	Stay on Substance search portal page	Select CE Route B: Wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation. Select either the "predicted" or "experimental" option. Check the details of the resulting substance.
4	Go to PMT identifier page	Search if substance 'perfluorooctanoic acid' is toxic. Check the details of 'perfluorooctanoic acid' – is it vPvM/PM/toxic/nontoxic?
5	Go to the Solution assessment page	Click on Route A, go to Emission prevention and read the route explanation.

Five individuals completed the test and provided feedback. Each participant's testing process was recorded from start to finish; however, there was no continuous recording between tasks. This makes quantitative analysis more challenging, as some users provided feedback while performing tasks, whereas others only gave their input during the final discussion round.

It should also be noted that during the testing for participants 3 to 5, internet connectivity issues caused delays in task completion. These delays did not reflect the tool's functionality but rather an external factor that affected the testing process.

One of the most prominent issues identified was that users did not realize that the navigation bar at the top of the page could be used to move between different sections of the DSF. This led to difficulties in accessing different pages efficiently. Additionally, some testers found the navigation bar too small or not prominent enough to be easily noticed.

On the homepage bar plot, some testers were unsure of what the selection criteria represented. They recommended that further clarification be provided, either through tooltips or additional descriptive text. One tester also suggested linking the DSF with other tools (e.g. the RIVM's PBT tool), which is commonly used in the Dutch chemical industry to evaluate substances.

The search functionality received mostly positive feedback, with users appreciating the inclusion of CAS numbers. However, several quality-of-life features and more data inclusion were suggested to improve the tool.

Most participants showed a strong interest in using the DSF as a tool to support the transition to safer, sustainable-by-design (SSbD) chemicals. However, aligning it more closely with national and EU regulatory frameworks could improve its usefulness to industry.

In general, users became more proficient in using the tool compared to the previous iteration. While the third evaluation session focused on overcoming usability barriers, the discussion in the fourth session shifted toward adding new functionalities that could complement the system and enhance its value. Although the list of suggested improvements was extensive, the most feasible and impactful functionalities were prioritized for implementation toward the end of the project.

This final evaluation was used to determine which functionalities needed to be implemented before the project's completion and to refine the interface for optimal usability based on the feedback received so far.

Significant development work in the last months of the project led to substantial changes in all the tool modules. These changes were made primarily to enhance usability and, secondly, to integrate new information received within the project, such as updates to the solutions and diagnosis modules. As a result, the focus shifted towards improving the user experience, incorporating as much relevant project information as possible, and providing links to complementary tools that extend the functionalities of the DSF.

5 Technical descriptions of the DSF modules

5.1 PMT Assessment

- **Technical backend.**

While the tool is divided into 5 modules, the backend is only split into 3 modules (referred as endpoints for clarification) depending on their main instances, which are either Substances, Solutions or Strategies. The PMT Assessment module uses the Substance Endpoint, which has many functions that can be summarized by providing different ways for the user to find the substance or substances of concern. The backend of this module consists of multiple endpoints that return lists of Substances, except in rare cases. All the functions are documented in the appendix **Substances Endpoint**.

The PMT Assessment uses a function that allows users to search for substances. This endpoint takes as input attributes that a substance might have and returns a list of all the substances that match these attributes. This is done by taking all the set attributes, such as CAS number, Sector of Use, or substance name, and removing all the substances that don't match. The attributes can be partially set, so it is possible to search for a substance with only a small part of the name, or to search for substances whose CAS number starts with a certain prefix.

- **Technical frontend.**

The frontend of the PMT Assessment is used to let users search for substances and display their values in a plot for a first assessment on the specified substances. The search function implements an autocomplete function that saves users from having to type the exact name of the substance they are interested in. The module is developed using Angular and PrimeNG components, and the plots are created using Plotly.

5.2 Diagnosis

- **Technical backend.**

The Diagnosis module uses functions implemented in the Substances Endpoint presented in the PMT Assessment section.

Because of the large amount of data related to a single Substance, the requests would often return data that is not necessary for the specific function requested, and this extra data would cause an increase in RAM usage in the server, affecting performance negatively and causing errors. To fix this, the backend implements JSON views, a technique that lets developers define specific attributes to be returned for each function, instead of the entire Substance instance. This way, data return was optimized for each request without adding unnecessary complexity in the backend or losing important data. The functions of the module are provided as endpoints. The main endpoint of this module is the substance relevance endpoint. This endpoint takes three coefficients, one each for persistence, mobility, and toxicity, and returns the top 30 substances of all the database according to the coefficients, giving priority according to them. A variation of this endpoint was created, which returns the 6 substances with the higher average of normalized persistence, mobility, toxicity, and kemiscore. Another important endpoint takes a Substance defined by the input and returns its 50 most similar substances, calculated using the Tanimoto Similarity of their canonical SMILES. This calculation is implemented using the rdkit library in a Python service, which is called by the backend using HTTP requests.

The module also provides two endpoints used for autocompleting purposes, one for chemical classes and one for substance names. The endpoints return lists of strings that match the query being passed by parameter.

Finally, the module has a group of endpoints that provide substances data in a processed form to be displayed in plots. One endpoint returns the 20 substances with higher median concentration value of all its samples. Two other endpoints identify a substance with the user input and return its samples data to create a violin plot of concentration values, and the average of all samples matching the selected substance's sector of use or product category, respectively.

- **Technical frontend.**

The Diagnosis component allows users to search for and analyze substances of interest through various interactive tools. This module interacts with multiple backend services that provide filtered substance lists based on different search and relevance criteria.

The entire module is implemented within an Angular service, which handles HTTPS requests to the backend and manages the received data. The retrieved information is displayed using PrimeNG components, ensuring a clear and intuitive user experience.

Search and Filtering Functionalities

Users can search for specific substances using various attributes: CAS Number, InChIKey, and Substance Name. Filters can be applied partially, meaning users can find substances by entering only a partial name or a fragment of the CAS number. To enhance user experience, the frontend implements autocomplete functionality, providing real-time substance name suggestions as users type.

Relevance Calculation and Visualization

The module includes a tool for calculating the most relevant substances based on the three key coefficients: Persistence, Mobility, and Toxicity. Results are displayed in an interactive table and through Plotly-generated graphs, allowing users to visualize relationships between these coefficients and the relevance of each substance.

A key functionality of the module is the similar substance search. Users can select a substance of interest, and the system will generate a list of the 30 most similar substances, presenting the results visually for easier interpretation.

5.3 Solutions

- **Technical backend.**

The backend of the Solutions module is centered around the Solution class, which does not have as many related classes as the Substances. The focus of the Solutions module in the backend is to provide either a list of Solutions or the specific information of one solution.

All the functions are documented in the appendix **Solutions** .

In this module there are two main endpoints. One returns the entire list of Solutions found in the database, and the other lets the user search for a single solution by name. There is no endpoint that returns all the solutions linked to a substance, because this functionality can be obtained from the Substances module. Using any endpoints that return substances, all the substances are returned together with their linked instances, such as the solutions. The endpoints that return solutions contain the substances related to the solutions, but not the solutions related to the substances since this would cause an infinite recursion error inside the JSON return value. JSON Views are used to fix this problem.

- **Technical frontend.**

The Solutions module in the frontend is designed to enable users to browse and search for solutions available in the database. Its primary function is to fetch and display internal and external solutions lists.

The module's logic is implemented in an Angular service, which is responsible for making HTTPS requests to the backend and managing the received data. The information is presented in a structured format using PrimeNG, ensuring a smooth and intuitive user experience.

The frontend includes a view that displays the complete list of solutions available in the database. This list is fetched through a request to the backend and shown in an interactive PrimeNG table, allowing users to efficiently sort and filter the data.

When viewing an individual solution, the frontend also displays the substances related to that solution, providing users with a comprehensive view of its impact.

5.4 Strategies

- **Technical backend.**

The Strategies module is very similar to the Solutions module, with one key difference. Like the Solutions module, it has one endpoint that returns the total list of Strategies in the database, and one that lets the user search a single Strategy by name. However, the technical backend is not being used in this module since the last version of the strategies module is fully visual and links to already published Zenodo documents. Therefore, the developed endpoints are left as a piece of code that could be valuable in future development, since including documents in a local database is common.

All the functions are documented in the appendix **Strategies** .

In addition to these two endpoints, since each Strategy has a linked document explaining it, the backend has an endpoint that lets the users download these files. This is done by using the Content Disposition Header in the Response of the Request sent to the backend. With this Header, it can be indicated that the data sent in the Response is an attachment and its type, such as PDF or CSV. Then, the data of the file is sent through the Response as an octet stream, which is pieced together again by the browser and made available as the original file for download.

- **Technical frontend.**

The Strategies module in the frontend is like the Solutions module, with one key difference: each resource is associated with a document that users can download from Zenodo for more detailed information.

All the logic of the module is implemented in an Angular service, which manages communication with the backend via HTTPS requests. The retrieved data is presented clearly using PrimeNG, ensuring an intuitive and efficient user experience.

The frontend allows users to access the complete list of strategies.

5.5 Search Substances

- **Technical backend.**

This module also uses functions from the Substances Endpoint presented and defined in the PMT Assessment and Diagnosis sections. This module is used to present search results in a more detailed way, with all their available attributes. It uses the same endpoint as the PMT Assessment module, which lets users search for substances with partially defined attributes.

- **Technical frontend.**

The frontend of the Search Substances module provides a form for users to search for substances with partially defined attributes and presents the results in table format. The data presented in the table can also be downloaded as a CSV file, and multiple views for this information are provided.

6 Data gathering and the DSF database

To make the data available to the final user of the DSF, it is necessary to integrate it into a database. There are many different sources of data, each organized and stored in different ways and formats, such as Excel/CSV files, external REST API services, plain text, pdf files, and more. Since the DSF must provide this information to the user in an ordered and organized manner, the data must be transformed from their original formats to a standard format. For this reason, the DSF Database defines a standard format that guides on how to store the data and provides functionalities to store the data in an efficient way, not only related to storage usage, but also for querying capabilities.

Data Sources

The project data is extracted from the NORMAN Database and other data sources, including the European Chemicals Agency “ECHA”⁶ online database. Regarding the NORMAN Database, most data has been extracted from both the Substance Database “SusDat”⁷ and the Chemical Occurrence Data “EMPODAT”⁸ Modules, but also the Suspect List Exchange “SLE”⁹ module was useful for determining a total list of available substances.

To exploit this data and make it available to the users of the DSF, a CSV file was created under task 5.2, grouping data from multiple sources and presenting it in a format that is both readable and easy to process with code. The creation of this file is reported in D5.1¹⁰. All data sources are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Data sources.

Data Source	Use	Format
NORMAN Substance Database “SusDat”	Data related to substance identification, such as CAS Number or InchiKey.	JSON (HTTP Request)
NORMAN Chemical Occurrence Data “EMPODAT”	Chemical concentration values.	JSON (HTTP Request)
NORMAN Suspect List Exchange “SLE”	List of all InchiKeys available in the NORMAN Database.	TXT
European Chemicals Agency Database	Sectors of use of the different substances.	TXT
Task 5.2	Data on substances studied in the project and all their related attributes. Used in all the frontend modules.	CSV
PROMISCES Deliverable 5.4	Data on solutions used in the frontend solutions module.	XLS

⁶ <https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>

⁷ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/susdat/>

⁸ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/empodat/>

⁹ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/SLE/>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14204373>

Data Processing and Uploading

The processing of the data and its upload to the database is performed using a Python script. The process consists of obtaining the data from the relevant sources and parsing to extract the data corresponding to the data model of the database. The sources are the previously mentioned CSV file and the NORMAN Database REST API, accessible using HTTP requests. This process is not automated since it is only run once to populate the database.

The data from the various sources is parsed line by line, with each line defining an instance. This process consists of recovering the relevant information from the respective key, which could be a column of the CSV file, or a key of the JSON object returned by an HTTP request to one of the endpoints of the NORMAN Database API. In some specific keys, the data is modified to fit in the database. For example, the synonyms of a substance are parsed from a long string split by commas and other key-value pairs to a Python list of strings, with one synonym on each string, as seen in Figure 8.

Cell in CSV file:
 "Sulfaclozine,Sulfachloropyrazine,Sulfachlorpyrazin"
 ↓
 JSON sent in POST Request:

```
{
  ...
  "nameSynonyms": [
    "Sulfaclozine",
    "Sulfachloropyrazine",
    "Sulfachlorpyrazin"
  ],
  ...
}
```

Figure 8 - Example of nameSynonyms processing when uploading data.

Also, data corresponding to entities related to the Substance entity, like for example the Sector Of Use, are parsed as its own object encased inside the larger object of the Substance, as seen in Figure 9. Finally, all numeric data is formatted as a number, parsing its value from the string, and transforming it into the required type, which may or may not include decimals.

JSON sent in POST Request: <pre>{ ... "casNumber": "102-65-8" "sectorsOfUse": [{ "name": "Cleaning agents" }], "name": "Bleaching agents" }, ... }</pre>	Instances created in database: Substance "102-65-8" └ SectorOfUse "Cleaning Agents" └ SectorOfUse "Bleaching Agents"
---	---

Figure 9 - Example of nested instance processing when uploading data.

Once an instance is parsed, it is uploaded to the database by sending a POST request to an endpoint in the backend API. The configuration in the POST request transforms the body of the request, which contains all the data previously parsed and represents an instance in JSON format, to an instance of the object it represents in the Data Model. In some cases, it might also derive a related instance to the main instance, such as creating a Chemical Class related to a Substance. The instances are then uploaded to the database. To avoid uploading duplicates to the database, the function to save the instances automatically checks if an instance is already in the database by checking if another instance with the same primary key already exists. If it does not, the new instance is created successfully, but if it does, the original instance is modified with the data from the new instance. In addition, if the JSON object is not formatted correctly, the endpoint will return an erroneous code specifying what is wrong with the JSON object. Figure 10 shows an example of a complete request.

```
{
  'casNumber': '102-65-8',
  'ECNumber': '',
  'promiscesID': '',
  'normanSusDatID': 'NS00000001',
  'canonicalSMILES': 'NC1=CC=C(C=C1)S(=O)(=O)NC1=CN=CC(Cl)=N1',
  'nameSynonyms': ['Sulfaclozine'],
  'group': {'groupName': '', 'groupDescription': ''},
  'persistence': 0.1150954019017803,
  'mobility': 0.0,
  'toxicity': 0.0,
  'potentialEnvironmentEmissions': '',
  'addressedApplication': '',
  'CLPharmonised': 'False',
  'numericalData': {
    'PubChem_CID': 66890.0,
    'Monoiso_Mass': 284.013474,
    'M+H+': 285.02075,
    'M-H-': 283.006198,
    'ED_assessment_index': 0.1,
    'ED_reliab': 0.8,
    'ED_score_janus': 0.14199999999999999,
    'SCORE_vPvB': 0.158,
    'SCORE_SVHC': 0.799,
    'SCORE_PBT': 0.271,
    'B_score_exp': 3.406101238245704e-58,
    'P_score_conservative': 0.223,
    'P_score_average': 0.1150954019017803,
    'M_score_conservative': 0.4222469225821516,
    'B_score_conservative': 1.7220778081295828e-175,
    'B_score_robust': 3.406101238245704e-58,
    'score_multiplicative': 4.601360518144201,
    'PM_conservative_score': 0.3068567479066083,
    'PB_conservative_score': 1.9596513751504292e-88,
  },
  'conservativeClassification': 'M(T)',
  'robustClassification': '(T)',
  'averageClassification': 'nP(T)',
  'ceRoutes': [],
  'sectorsOfUse': [],
  'chemicalClasses': [
    'Amines',
    'Aromatic amines',
    'Sulfonamides',
    'Sulfones'
  ],
  'concentrationValues': {
    'Waste water - Municipal': ['0.01601192302']
  }
}
```

Figure 10 - Example of a complete POST request.

Database Structure

The UML diagram in Figure 11 represents the Database Structure, with the data models corresponding to the different instances of the project.

Figure 11 - UML Diagram of the Database Structure of the DSF.

The Database Structure of the DSF is centered around the Substances. The Substance Class is the center of all the relations in the database and has many attributes, which can be classified in different types depending on their function.

The function of the first group is simply identifying the instance and being able to distinguish different substances between them. In this group, the attributes are the ID, a “Long” number without decimals that is automatically and sequentially assigned to new instances - the CAS number, EC Number, PROMISCES ID, NORMAN SusDat ID, and the canonical SMILES of the substance, all strings, and the name synonyms - a list of multiple strings. All the attributes that are simple strings are configured so that they must be unique in the database, since they are all attributes that are specific to each substance that cannot be repeated.

The second group consists of multiple attributes defining the substance’s qualities. It is formed by the chemical classes of the substance, a list of strings, and the potential environmental emissions, addressed applications, harmonized classification, and three variables representing the PMT classification: a conservative one, a robust one, and the average. All these variables are strings.

Finally, the last group has all the attributes that consist of numerical data of the substance. The substance has three BigDecimal attributes that represent persistence, mobility and toxicity, respectively. These three attributes are used to sort the substances, according to a priority value for each variable set by the user. Then, it has a map that links all other numerical data parameters with their BigDecimal value, and a map that links the name of the matrixes of substances, which represents the places from where chemical samples have been collected such as surface water or wastewater, to a list of BigDecimals of the concentration values of the substance in these samples.

Regarding relations, substances are linked to one Priority Group, at least one Circular Economy Route, and may or may not be connected to one or more different Sectors Of Use. The only attributes of these instances are the ID and strings used to identify them. This data is used in the search engine of the DSF.

Each Substance can also have relations to Samples, which are unique for each Substance, and they model a Sample extracted from the EMPODAT database, with its sample matrix type, the concentration of the Substance, sampling date and other information used for displaying and sorting in the frontend.

The Substances are also linked to Solutions. They may have any number of relationships, including none, although most Substances are linked to multiple Solutions and vice versa.

The Solution instance has a “Long” ID, a name, type, and addressed application in String, and two Boolean variables used to further detail how the solution works. The Solutions are also linked to at least one Strategy, which functions as a collection of Solutions that work well together.

The Solution instance also has a unique Solution Criteria instance. There are two possible types of Solution Criteria, either Recovery Criteria or Degradation Criteria. These two types of Solution Criteria have been modelled as subclasses of an abstract class Solution Criteria, since the two types have many variables in common, but it should not be possible to create a Solution Criteria that is not of one of these two types. All the variables of both types are BigDecimals, used to sort the solutions according to a priority set by the user, just like with the substances.

Frontend Structure

The web tool is built using the Angular¹¹ framework, with TypeScript¹² as the primary language for application coding. It integrates the following libraries and technologies:

- PrimeNG: A User Interface (UI) component library that includes tables, forms, and other elements, facilitating the creation of interactive and visually appealing interfaces.
- Plotly: A library used to generate interactive and visual charts.
- HTTPS connection with a REST API service: The application connects to the backend to retrieve dynamic data.
- Enables the coding of the main components: Substance, Diagnosis, Solution, PMT Assessment, and Strategy, which manage the views and user interactions.

Project Structure

The application follows the standard structure of an Angular project, ensuring that each module or functionality is properly isolated.

Folder and File Structure

The graphical user interface file system (shown in Figure 12) is structured following the logic:

- *node_modules*: Stores all the libraries and dependencies required for the project to function correctly.
- *src*: The main project directory, containing:
 - *app/*: Stores all Angular source code.
 - *models/*: Directory containing data models.
 - *dashboard/*: Manages the view related to the home page.
 - *pmt-assessment/*: Manages the view for the PMT assessment.
 - *pmt-identifier/*: Handles the diagnosis-related view.
 - *solution/*: Manages the Solution Assessment view.
 - *strategy/*: Manages the Strategy Creation view.
 - *substance-detail/*: Handles the Substance Detail view.
 - *substance-search/*: Manages the Substance Search view.
 - *services/*: Contains business logic services and manages interactions with the backend (REST API).
 - *app.main.component.ts*: The root component that defines the general UI structure and shared logic.
 - *app.module.ts*: The main module, where PrimeNG modules, services, and components are declared. It also imports and configures routing to manage views.
 - *app-routing.module.ts*: The routing configuration file that defines how navigation occurs between different components.

¹¹ <https://angular.dev/>

¹² <https://www.typescriptlang.org/>

- *assets/*: Stores static files such as images, icons, and other resources required by the app.
- *environments/*: Contains configuration files for different environments (development and production).

Figure 12 - Components, services and libraries structure.

Figure 13 visualizes the interaction between the UI and services using HTTP requests. The frontend manages all the different component-service interactions and requests the backend the needed data through the API REST interaction.

Figure 13 - Diagram interaction between the UI and services using HTTP request.

View Management with Angular and Routing

Angular uses a router to manage views. The `app-routing.module.ts` file defines application routes and links them to their respective components Figure 14.

Routes determine how views (DashboardComponent, AboutComponent, etc.) are assigned to specific URLs. The router handles view changes dynamically as users navigate through different sections.

This file configures the paths for accessing the following views:

- Diagnosis (/identifier)
- PMT Assessment (/assessment)
- Solution Assessment (/solution)
- Strategy Creation (/strategy)
- Substance Search (/substance)
- About (/about)
- Cookies Policy (/cookies)
- Privacy Policy (/privacy)
- Legal Notice (/legal)

Additionally, a default route is set for the home page.

```
> import { NgModule } from '@angular/core'; ...

const routes: Routes = [
  {
    path: '', component: AppMainComponent,
    children: [
      { path: '', component: DashboardComponent },
      { path: 'identifier', component: PmtIdentifierComponent },
      { path: 'assessment', component: PmtAssessmentComponent },
      { path: 'solution', component: SolutionComponent },
      { path: 'strategy', component: StrategyComponent },
      { path: 'substance', component: SubstanceSearchComponent },
      { path: 'about', component: AboutComponent },
      { path: 'cookies', component: CookiesPolicyComponent },
      { path: 'privacy', component: PrivacyPolicyComponent },
      { path: 'legal', component: LegalNoticeComponent }
    ]
  },
];

@NgModule({
  imports: [RouterModule.forRoot(routes)],
  exports: [RouterModule]
})
export class AppRoutingModule { }
```

Figure 14 - Angular routing file.

7 Deploying process and published code

The deployment of the DSF is managed using Docker, a containerization technology that enables developers to package applications into standardized units called images. Each image includes the application code, configurations, libraries, and dependencies, ensuring seamless deployment across different environments. With Docker, setting up the application on a new machine requires only a single command, as all prerequisites are automatically installed.

To manage multiple interconnected containers within the application, Docker Compose is utilized. This tool simplifies the orchestration of various components, such as databases and microservices, which are available as pre-configured Docker images, eliminating the need for manual installation.

The PROMISCES DSF is deployed using a Docker Compose configuration with four distinct containers:

1. **PostgreSQL Database:** Provided as a Docker image, allowing for easy deployment without manual installation.
2. **Java Spring Boot Backend:** Handles the core application logic, including database interactions through Spring Data JPA.
3. **Python Web Service:** Supports the Substance Similarity function by executing a specific algorithm available in a Python library. This service is called by the Spring Boot backend when needed.
4. **Frontend (Angular + Nginx):** Hosts the user interface and manages requests through a Nginx web server.

At an initial step, the DSF is deployed on a dedicated server at Eurecat facilities for testing and demonstrations. However, the Docker Compose setup allows for effortless deployment on any compatible machine with minimal effort.

For version control and code management, GitHub is used. This platform enables developers to publish, collaborate, and manage Git repositories efficiently. The public GitHub repositories¹³ allow anyone to access, download, and deploy the DSF. External contributors may also contribute to the project or develop alternative versions of the tool.

¹³ <https://github.com/Applied-Artificial-Intelligence-Eurecat/Promiscses-back>

<https://github.com/Applied-Artificial-Intelligence-Eurecat/Promiscses-Front>

8 NORMAN and the future of the DSF

The development of the DSF was completed within the scope of the project, with this deliverable marking a key milestone for the final resulting version. The tool integrates various functionalities, incorporating data from multiple external repositories as well as project-specific sources. However, a strategy is needed to ensure its future use beyond the project's duration.

Throughout the project, discussions have taken place with NORMAN network¹⁴ to facilitate the inclusion of the DSF in its NORMAN Database System, ensuring its long-term maintenance. The network will deploy the tool within its infrastructure, incorporating it into its tool catalog, which will enable future improvements to be implemented as part of its strategic planning. To integrate the tool into their system, knowledge transfer and deployment support meetings will be conducted, along with the provision of relevant technical documentation and open, easily accessible code.

While NORMAN will ultimately be responsible for deploying the DSF, PROMISCES identified several functionalities that could enhance the tool but were not implemented due to resource or data limitations.

- The home page currently presents an explanatory text about the tool, which can sometimes be difficult to digest and even unengaging for a first-time user. This could be improved with diagrams or animations to enhance user engagement.
- The navigation bar could be supplemented with relevant icons to improve usability and help users better understand the tool.
- Some functionalities (such as the diagnosis module) require significant computing resources and take a long time to execute. To improve performance, potential solutions include upgrading hardware or optimizing queries and code operations.
- The strategies module provides a list of options based on user needs, along with relevant links, but it could be further improved in the future as the scientific community defines more tailored strategies for different cases.
- There is a lack of harmonization in the parameters associated with each substance. While most substances comply with CAS-number identification, other parameters (such as persistence or mobility) are not yet fully defined and will be added over time. Functionalities that rely on these parameters (such as PMT Assessment) must be monitored and potentially adjusted to ensure accuracy.
- One of the most ambitious but impactful future developments would be the integration of AI into the system. By incorporating generative AI agents, the tool could provide an interactive e-learning environment that offers real-time assistance, improving navigation, enhancing functionality usage, and offering explanations of obtained results.

¹⁴ <https://www.norman-network.com/>

9 Appendix

A. Low-Fidelity Prototype

XXX index

Features

PMT identifier ▶

Ensure you have identified a persistent mobile toxic substance according to the XX database.

[Follow promisces on linkedin](#)

[Follow promisces on twitter](#)

Search substances ▶

Go to the substance search portal.

[Visit our web page](#)

Need PMT assessment ▶

Receive a personal assessment on a PMT case. Treatment solution, risk assessment, and more.

Substance name is visible when cursor is moving over the plot

Substance details

[Go back](#)

<p>▼ General description</p> <p>Substance name</p> <p>Substance group</p> <p>Addressed application</p> <p>CE route</p>
<p>▶ Available solutions</p>
<p>▶ Identified strategies</p>

Generic details ? Help

Solution type: Addressed applications: CE route:

Criteria

■ Applicability
■ Efficiency

■ Availability
■ Co-effects

■ Energetic cost
■ Economic cost

Reset options Check

The criteria options change depending on the generic details introduced.

Substance: **Select and download a strategy**

- | | |
|-------------------|---|
| Strategy 1, title | |
| Strategy 2, title | |
| Strategy 3, title | |
| Strategy 4, title | |

B. High-Fidelity Prototype

PROMISCES Decision Support Framework

Please change the weights of the criteria according to your preference, from most important (=10) to not important (=0)

Substance criteria selection

Persistence

Potential environment emissions

Mobility

Criterion 5

Toxicity

Criterion 6

Substance relevance by criterion

Features

PMT Identifier ▶

Ensure you have identified a persistent mobile toxic substance according to several databases.

Search substances ▶

Go to the substance search portal.

PMT Assessment ▶

Receive a personal assessment on a PMT case.

Solution assessment ▶

Search our solutions database for potential relevant solutions for your case.

Strategies ▶

Check our developed strategies to tackle specific cases of PMTs actions in specific sectors

Find us on

- promisces.eu
- [LinkedIn Profile](#)
- [@Promisces_EU](#)

Substance Details

▼ General description		
Substance name	And more...	...
Substance group		
Adressed Application		
▼ Available Solutions		
Solution name 1	Solution type 1	...
Solution name 2	Solution type 2	
...	...	
▶ Identified Strategies		

PMT identifier

Receive information on whether your substance is considered a Persistent, Mobile and Toxic (PMT) or very Persistent very Mobile (vPvM) substance based on experimental data or modelled indicators.

Substance Name

Search

Substance Details

<p>▼ General description</p> <p>Substance name</p> <p>Substance group</p> <p>Adressed Application</p>
<p>▶ Available Solutions</p>
<p>▶ Identified Strategies</p>

Substance search portal

Introduce different information to find substances related to your case

Substance Name
 Type of solution
 Solution name
 Substance group

CE route
 Chemical class
 sector of use
 Followed strategy

Range of results: **XX / XX / XXX**

Solution assessment

Generic Details

Solution type Adressed Application CE Route

Substance to apply

Criteria

Please change the weights of the criteria according to your preference, from most important (=10) to not important (=0)

Criterion 1

Criterion 2

Criterion 3

Criterion 4

Criterion 5

Criterion 6

Solutions sorted by criterion

Solution details

▼ General description

Solution name

Solution type

Adressed Application

CE route

▶ Related substances

▶ Identified Strategies

Strategies

Substance

Strategy 1 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 2 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 3 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 4 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 5 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 6 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 7 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>
Strategy 8 Title Name, Title Name, Title Name, Title Name,	<input type="button" value="Download"/>

PMT assessment

Concerned about a specific PMT substance?

Substance Name

PMT assessment

Concerned about a specific PMT substance?

How do I know I have PMT in my process?

Select your CE route

Sector of use

Chemical class

Relevant substances for the XXX Route .

Substance 1 - 20 3423

Range of results: **XX / XX / XXX**

Sort by

« « Pag 1 / 50 » »

PMT 1	
Detection 1	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.</p>
Monitoring 1	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum.</p>
<input type="button" value="Check all details"/>	
PMT 2	
PMT 3	
PMT 4	

C. Backend Functions Documentation

D. Substances Endpoint

GET	/substances/	
Get All Substances		
Returns a page from the list of all the substances in the database, with the page number and number of items in a page set by the user.		
Returns	List of Substance	
Parameters	pageNumber	Used for offset in returning registers
	registersPerPage	How many registers to return
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the user requested for more registers than there are in the database
	204 No Content	If the database is empty

GET	/substances/autocomplete/	
Get Autocomplete Options For Substance Name		
Returns a list of names of Substances in the database that match a string. The first results check if the name starts by the string, and the latter check if the name simply contains the string.		
Returns	List of String	
Parameters	substanceName	String to search for
	Errors	204 No Content
		If the search returned no results

GET	/substances/chemicalclasses/	
Get List Options For Chemical Classes		
Returns a list of all chemical classes in the database. Used to create dropdown options.		
Returns	List of String	
Errors	204 No Content	If the query returned no results

POST	/substances/details/	
Get Substance Details		
Returns a Substance object, finding it by either the CAS Number or any of the names.		
Returns	Substance	
Body JSON	name OR cas_n	The name or the CAS Number of the substance
Errors	400 Bad Request	The request body does not have name or cas_n
	404 Not Found	The substance was not found in the database

POST	/substances/search/	
Get All Substances That Match A Filter		
Returns a page from the list of all the substances in the database, with the page number and number of items in a page set by the user, after filtering by the desired criteria. All the parameters in the body are optional.		
Returns	List of Substance	
Parameters	pageNumber	Used for offset in returning registers
	registersPerPage	How many registers to return
Body JSON	substance_name	String, name or part of the names to accept
	solution_type	String, types of solution to accept
	solution_name	String, name or part of the solution names to accept
	substance_group	String, groups to accept
	ce_route	String, CE Routes to accept
	chemical_class	String, chemical classes to accept
	use_sector	String, sectors of use to accept
	followed_strategy	String, name or part of the strategy names to accept
	Inchikey	String, name or part of the substance's inchikey
	experimental	Boolean, to include or not substances with experimental data
	predicted	Boolean, to include or not substances with predicted data
Errors	204 No Content	If the search returned no results
	400 Bad Request	If the user requests for more registers than there are in the database

POST	/substances/relevance/	
Get Substances By Relevance		
Returns the 6 more important substances according to persistence, mobility and toxicity, with the attributes having different weights, set by the user.		
Returns	List Of Substance	
Body JSON	persistence	How important the persistence value is from 0 to 10
	mobility	How important the mobility value is from 0 to 10
	toxicity	How important the toxicity value is from 0 to 10

POST	/substances/counts/{filterBy}/	
Get Substance Counts		
Returns the count of how many substances belong to each different classification after filtering by either sectorsOfUse or chemicalClasses.		
Returns	JSON	
Parameters	filterBy	sectorsOfUse or chemicalClasses, which to filter by
Body JSON	values	The accepted values in the filter
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the filterBy parameter does not match the accepted values

GET	/substances/violinplot/	
Get Data For Violin Plot		
Returns the data for sample matrices and concentration values of a Substance condensed in an easier format for plotting.		
Returns	JSON, keys are String and values are list of BigDecimal	
Body JSON	name OR cas_n OR inchikey	The name or the CAS Number or the inchikey of the substance
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the body is missing all accepted variables
	404 Not Found	If the substance was not found

GET	/substances/targetedchemical/	
Get Data For Targeted Chemical Plot		
Returns a list of the 20 substances with higher median concentration value in its samples.		
Returns	List of Substance	

GET	/substances/kemiscore/	
Get Top Substances By Kemiscore Relevance		
Returns a list of the 20 substances with higher normalized Persistence, Mobility, Toxicity, and Kemiscore average.		
Returns	List of Substance	

GET	/substances/similarSubstances/	
Get Most Similar Substances		
Returns the most similar substances of the specified substance using the Tanimoto Similarity.		
Returns	List of substance name, likeness to original substance, Persistence, Mobility, Toxicity, and Kemiscore.	
Body JSON	name OR cas_n OR inchikey	The name or the CAS Number or the inchikey of the substance
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the body is missing all accepted variables
	404 Not Found	If the substance was not found
	500 Server Error	If there were issues in the connection between the backend and the service

GET	/substances/averagescores/	
Get Average Scores Of Substance's PC or Sector Of Use		
Given a substance, return the average Persistence, Mobility, and Kemiscore of the PC or Sectors Of Use of this substance.		
Returns	List of item name, Persistence, Mobility, Toxicity, and Kemiscore.	
Parameters	groupby	"pc" or "sector_of_use" to define which category to use to filter
Body JSON	name OR cas_n OR inchikey	The name or the CAS Number or the inchikey of the substance
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the body is missing all accepted variables or groupby parameter is missing or not an accepted value
	404 Not Found	If the substance was not found

E. Solutions Endpoint

GET	/solutions/	
Get All Solutions		
Returns a page from the list of all the solutions in the database, with the page number and number of items in a page set by the user.		
Returns	List of Solution	
Parameters	pageNumber	Used for offset in returning registers
	registersPerPage	How many registers to return
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the user requested for more registers than there are in the database
	204 No Content	If the database is empty

POST	/solutions/details/	
Get Solution Details		
Returns a Solution object after finding it the Solution name.		
Returns	Solution	
Body JSON	name	The name of the solution
Errors	400 Bad Request	The request body does not have name
	404 Not Found	The solution was not found in the database

F. Strategies Endpoint

GET	/strategies/	
Get All Strategies		
Returns a list of all the strategies in the database.		
Returns	List of Strategy	
Errors	204 No Content	If the database is empty

POST	/strategies/details/	
Get Strategy Details		
Returns a Strategy object finding it by its name.		
Returns	Strategy	
Body JSON	name	The name of the strategy
Errors	400 Bad Request	The request body does not have name
	404 Not Found	The strategy was not found in the database

POST	/strategies/related/	
Get Strategies Related To A Substance		
Returns a list of Strategies related to a substance by checking for the strategies of the solutions related to the substance.		
Returns	List of Strategy	
Body JSON	substance_name OR substance_cas	The name or the CAS number of the substance
Errors	400 Bad Request	The request body does not have substance_name or substance_cas
	404 Not Found	The substance was not found in the database

POST	/strategies/download/	
Download A File		
Returns the data in bytes of a file with the Content Disposition header so the browser detects it as a file and lets the user download it to their device.		
Returns	Octet Stream	
Body JSON	filename	The filename to download
Errors	400 Bad Request	If the body does not contain filename
	404 Not Found	If the file was not found